

BEYOND PETROPLASTICS

**Expert Insights on Biobased and
Biodegradable Material Substitutes
and Alternatives to Conventional
Plastics**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This expert guide supports the Global Plastics Treaty by providing science-based insights on bio-based and biodegradable materials (BBMs) as an alternative to conventional plastics. The guide highlights both the opportunities and the challenges of BBMs, ensuring they are not only circular but also safe for human health and the environment.

Purpose

The report aims to address gaps in technical understanding of BBMs within the treaty process. It provides policymakers and stakeholders with evidence on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approaches, chemical safety, end-of-life (EoL) strategies, and the role of standards and certification in building trust and avoiding greenwashing.

Key Findings

- BBMs will play a significant role in replacing the most problematic plastic applications, particularly where persistent microplastics or waste mismanagement are a concern.
- SSbD principles are essential to ensure BBMs are safe, sustainable, and compatible with circularity from the outset.
- Additives and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) remain a risk factor in BBMs just as in conventional plastics and require full transparency and elimination of chemicals of concern.
- Biodegradability and compostability are context-dependent and must be verified with harmonised standards and credible certification systems.
- BBMs are most effective when designed for multiple EoL pathways (e.g., material recycling, composting, thermal recovery), reducing the risk of mismanagement.
- A science-based advisory mechanism is needed to inform treaty implementation and updates.

Recommendations

1. Require Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approaches for all plastics and BBMs.
2. Mandate full chemical transparency and safety oversight, including a global “Red List” of hazardous substances.
3. Support safer material innovation through R&D and adoption of inherently safer additives and polymers.
4. Implement harmonized standards and third-party certification to verify biodegradability and safety.
5. Design for multiple end-of-life pathways, ensuring compatibility with local infrastructure.
6. Establish a science-based advisory mechanism to review and update evidence and guide treaty decisions.

INTRODUCTION

To be effective, the Global Plastics Treaty must go beyond reducing plastic production and improving collection and recycling systems. It must capitalize on the market shift towards safer and sustainable material systems. Whilst reducing plastic production and improving collection are critical interventions, they alone cannot address the systemic issues posed by conventional plastics, especially those with no economically viable or circular end-of-life. A successful treaty must also support the transition that is already occurring toward safer and more sustainable material systems.

The Treaty, as reflected in the evolving draft texts, has consistently recognized the role of “alternatives and non-plastic substitutes” to address plastic pollution from a full life-cycle approach. While this terminology lacks technical clarity and an agreed-upon official definition within the treaty process, it highlights a growing need for attention on sustainable materials beyond conventional plastics. This document focuses on one category of what is broadly discussed as “alternatives and substitutes”: biobased and biodegradable materials (BBMs). BBMs include polymeric materials such as chitin, phycocolloids (i.e. seaweed extracts), cellulose, starch, polysaccharides, and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), among others. BBMs combine two essential attributes that contribute meaningfully to reducing fossil resource dependency, enhancing environmental integrity, and

supporting the development of safe and circular material and product systems.

BBMs will play a vital role in replacing conventional plastics particularly in the most problematic and unsustainable applications. Although currently small in comparison to the global plastics market, BBMs are gaining momentum, with growing evidence of their potential to advance the treaty’s goals: preventing pollution, enabling circularity, and avoiding persistent microplastics. Consequently, BBMs have received widespread global support from governments. Governments have taken meaningful steps to enable substitution with BBMs, especially in critical sectors where harmful substances and microplastics risk entering the food-chain, such as agriculture, aquaculture, and food-contact packaging, with regulatory oversight for safety via mandatory tests and performance requirements.

A group of independent experts developed this technical guide on BBMs to present science-driven insights on technical aspects of BBMs that often cause concern or confusion, and to clarify their potential role as substitutes to conventional plastics. This guide brings together evidence and expert insights to inform policy design, risk mitigation, and the safe and effective adoption of BBMs.

Section I is dedicated to the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework, a holistic approach that promotes circular design. It resembles Life Cycle Assessment methodologies but expands them throughout the whole life cycle of the material, addressing safety and impacts on the environment, society, and economy.

Section II examines the chemical safety dimensions of BBMs, highlighting the potential presence of harmful additives similar to those found in conventional plastics. To avoid repeating the mistakes of conventional plastics, all substitutes and alternatives, including BBMs, must be verified, and comply with high safety standards from the outset.

Section III presents the diverse spectrum of end-of-life options for BBMs, compared to conventional non-biodegradable plastics. These include composting and anaerobic digestion, options characterized by significant variability and high degree of technical complexity.

Section IV discusses the standards and certification systems needed to verify biodegradability and other key features of BBMs. These systems are essential to unlocking the full safety and sustainability potential of BBMs, while preventing misleading claims and reducing the risk of persistent microplastic pollution.

Section V concludes with targeted recommendations to help align the systemic adoption of BBMs with the goals and implementation mechanisms of the Global Plastics Treaty.

Terminology

Biodegradation: the process by which microorganisms break down organic matter into carbon dioxide, water and biomass under aerobic conditions (when oxygen is present) and also methane under anaerobic conditions (in the absence of oxygen).

Persistent microplastics: plastic particles, smaller than 5 mm, that do not break down in the environment and therefore accumulate over time. They are a concern due to their persistence, mobility, and potential harm to ecosystems and potentially human health.

Non-persistent microplastics: plastic particles, smaller than 5mm, that do slowly or more rapidly break down in the environment and do not build up in the ecosystem. All materials degrading will go through the microplastics stage, the difference is that biodegradable ones will generate non-persistent microplastics as opposed to persistent ones generated by conventional plastics.

Fig 1: Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework (VISS project, 2025)

1 SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN (SSbD) FRAMEWORK

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To responsibly scale BBMs as replacement for problematic plastics, safety and sustainability considerations must be embedded from the earliest stages of product development. The Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework^{1, 2, 3} is a holistic approach developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) to **ensure that new chemicals, materials, products and processes are inherently safe for people and the environment and sustainable throughout their life cycle; therefore, avoiding harmful decisions for the environment** from the design phase.

Overall, the SSbD is aligned with Treaty goals (Article 5 — Plastic Product Design) as it addresses directly Paragraphs 1 (a and b) as it proposes to improve the (re)design of plastic products, including biobased

materials, to increase their sustainability and circularity while fostering research, innovation, development and use of sustainable and safer alternatives and non-plastic substitutes. A central pillar of SSbD is the rigorous assessment and elimination or minimization of hazardous substances throughout the value chain.

Moreover, other relevant principles of SSbD aim to optimise resource efficiency (focusing on reducing material and energy consumption throughout the lifecycle), promote circularity by encouraging the reuse, recycling, and recovery of materials, minimizing waste generation, and ensuring social and economic benefits, considering the broader societal impacts and economic viability of innovations.

SSbD Principle / Goal	What SSbD Means	How it Links to Article 5 of Chair's Text
1. Hazard Minimization (Safety First)	Exclude harmful chemicals when plastic substitutes are manufactured.	Art. 5(a)ii: "promote the use of safe and sustainable additives." Art. 5(b): "sustainable and safer alternatives."
2. Resource Efficiency (Less is More)	Optimizing material/energy use; reducing waste throughout the lifecycle.	Art. 5(a): "contribute to sustainable production and consumption of plastics by increasing reuse and recycling..." Art. 5(b): "...potential for waste reduction and reuse..."
3. Circularity Promotion (Looping Resources)	Designing for easy reuse, recycling, composting.	Art. 5(a): "...increasing reuse and recycling... and recycled content targets." Art. 5(a)ii: "Improve the durability, reusability, refillability, refurbishability, repairability and recyclability..." Art. 5(a)iii: "ensure disposal of plastic products in an environmentally sound manner in accordance with the waste hierarchy."
4. Holistic Assessment (Big Picture View)	Considering environmental, human health, social, & economic impacts.	Art. 5(b): "...taking into account environmental, economic, social and human health aspects..."
5. Proactive Approach (Design it Right from the Start)	Embedding sustainability & safety before scale-up, preventing future problems. Designing products whose properties meet consumers' demands and are compatible with safe end-of-life options.	Art. 5(a): "improve plastic product design, in pursuit of circular economy approaches..." Art. 5(b): "foster research, innovation, development and use of sustainable and safer alternatives..." SSbD is the methodology to design these.
6. LCA Integration (Data-Driven Decisions)	Using LCAs to quantify impacts & inform design choices.	Art. 5(b): "...based on life cycle assessments and best available science..." SSbD guides how LCA insights are applied to design decisions.
7. Avoiding Regrettable Substitution (No More False Solutions)	Ensures new alternatives truly improve impacts across the board, not just shifting problems.	Art. 5(b): "...sustainable and safer alternatives..." SSbD is the safeguard to ensure these alternatives genuinely reduce overall burdens, preventing unintended negative consequences that would undermine the Article's intent.

Table 1: SSbD framework alignment with the Treaty's Product Design Objectives

Key Dimensions of Sustainable Design

The SSbD approach integrates innovation/functionality considerations across four key dimensions (safety, environmental, social, and economic sustainability) throughout the design, production, use, and end-of-life of chemicals, materials, products and processes. This comprehensive evaluation ensures that improvements in one area do not lead to unintended negative consequences in others.

The **safety dimension** involves integrating safety considerations into the development and production process of BBMs from the conceptual stage. To avoid unverified claims, biodegradation tests must be thoroughly performed and safety and toxicity of bio-based plastics assessed.

The environmental dimension is technically covered by the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), whose objective is to consider impacts along the entire chemical/ material life cycle using, assessing several environmental impact categories. SSbD explicitly integrates LCA principles by requiring a holistic, lifecycle perspective in design choices. It goes beyond traditional LCA by also incorporating intrinsic safety aspects from the outset. It is important to highlight that, although LCA has traditionally been used reactively to assess existing products, its

application is increasingly expanding into proactive contexts. This includes scenario planning, design optimization, and circular economy strategy development. This proactive approach, particularly exemplified by SSbD, also considers impacts often overlooked by traditional LCA, such as the end-of-life of plastics and feedstock circularity, phases where BBMs often demonstrate significant sustainability advantages.

The social dimension is covered by the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of products⁴ considering five categories of stakeholders: workers, value chain actors, society, local community, and consumers. Finally, the economic dimension is addressed using the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) approach which is the opportunity to cover the economic considerations (such as cost efficiency, resource optimization, equipment, installation and operational efficiency). In this regard, it must be demonstrated how biodegradable plastics biodegrade successfully under specific conditions and are instead durable and stable during the use phase. For this reason, BBMs are compatible with reuse and recycle strategies.

Performance and Impact Assessment Tools

The SSbD is composed of two phases: the (re)design phase, which proposes design guiding principles and categories to support the development of the novel products, and the safety and sustainability assessment phase, which evaluates performance across all four dimensions. Although at its initial stage, following the SSbD approach, and particularly the LCA dimension, it is relevant to support plastic pollution mitigation and prevent unsustainable practices in the sector.

SSbD is fundamentally about accounting for risks in design choices by adopting a preventive approach. It mandates the consideration of potential hazards and risks at every stage of the design process, well before a product or process is scaled up or commercialized. This involves:

- Early hazard identification: Systematically identifying potential hazards associated with raw materials, intermediates, final products, and their byproducts.
- Risk assessment and management: Quantifying and evaluating identified risks, and then implementing strategies to reduce or eliminate them through design modifications.

- Iterative design: Encouraging a feedback loop where initial designs are assessed for safety and sustainability, and then refined based on the findings.
- Multi-criteria analysis: Using a range of indicators (as described above) to assess various types of risks (e.g., environmental, human health, social, economic).
- Transparency and communication: Documenting design choices and their associated risks, allowing for informed decision-making and communication with stakeholders.

This proactive approach minimizes the likelihood of unintended negative consequences emerging later in the product's lifecycle.

SSbD acts as a critical tool to avoid regrettable substitution by:

- Holistic Assessment, requiring a comprehensive evaluation of alternatives across their entire lifecycle and considering all aspects of safety and sustainability, not just a single dimension.
- Shifting the focus from reactive risk management (dealing with problems after they arise) to proactive hazard elimination and risk reduction at the design stage.
- Encouraging systematic comparison of different alternatives against a set of robust SSbD criteria to ensure that the chosen substitute genuinely offers an improvement across all relevant parameters.
- Prioritizing the design of materials with inherently safer and more sustainable properties from a molecular level.
- Promoting solutions that contribute to broader systemic sustainability goals, rather than merely solving an isolated problem.

SSbD is a necessary tool to avoid repeating the failures of conventional plastics. Embedding this practice in treaty mechanisms would support innovation pathways that are not only circular, but fundamentally safer for people and the planet. A practical application of the SSbD framework is exemplified by the **ViSS project** (see Annex I), a European-funded initiative (Project Grant No. 101081931). It demonstrates a safe and sustainable **PHBV value chain** for food packaging, transforming industrial food residues into high-performance food packaging. In ViSS, **PHBV**, a bio-based and biodegradable copolymer from the **PHAs family**, is produced intracellularly by microorganisms using industrial organic residues. The resulting PHBV will be formulated and compounded to create high-performance food packaging, validated for both mechanical recyclability and biodegradability.

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ADDITIVES & CHEMICALS

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Building on the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework in Section I, this section addresses one of the most critical yet often overlooked dimensions of safety and sustainability: the chemical composition of BBMs. While these materials are often assumed to be benign, their full impact depends on what is added during production, processing, and use. To fully realise their potential as safer and more sustainable solutions, it is critical to address the use of harmful chemicals in their production and lifecycle.

Key Impact 1: Human Health

Plastics can harm people through chemical leaching; BBMs must not repeat this. Conventional plastics are well-documented sources of chemical exposure, leaching additives such as plasticizers, Ultraviolet (UV) stabilizers, and residual monomers into food and the environment. UNEP's 2023 technical report identifies over

13,000 chemicals associated with plastics, many with known or suspected toxic effects⁵. Migration studies have shown these substances can enter food from packaging and other contact materials, even at low levels, contributing to endocrine disruption and other health effects⁶.

BBMs offer the potential for a safer material platform but only if chemicals of concern are identified and eliminated. Current evidence suggests this opportunity remains underutilized. In fact, over 150 chemicals of concern have already been identified in bio-based materials which are also listed in PlastChem's Red-List that highlights currently unregulated but high-risk substances^{7,8}. Notable examples include endocrine-disrupting phthalates (e.g., bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, dibutyl phthalate) found in PLA and PHA products⁹, and bisphenol-A (BPA) detected

in PLA cups, PBAT/PLA compostable bags, and bio-PET (Biobased Polyethylene Terephthalate) bottles¹⁰. This raises food-contact safety concerns and underscores the need for truly safer material innovation that excludes harmful additives and processing chemicals.

Key Impact 2: Environmental Fate and Biodegradation Interference

Additives can compromise biodegradability and other EoL options, extending environmental harm and undermining the environmental sustainability of BBMs. Some plastic additives have been shown to inhibit microbial activity critical to biodegradation, leading to persistence of BBM-derived microplastics. For example, benzotriazole-type UV stabilizers and certain antioxidants leaching from plastic debris have been found to accumulate in sediments and impair microbial communities responsible for natural degradation¹¹. This can extend the environmental lifespan of microplastic particles and increase risks of bioaccumulation and ecosystem toxicity, particularly in marine and soil environments where microplastics and associated chemicals infiltrate food chains. As an example, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has also raised concerns about biodegradable plastic mulch films used in agriculture, highlighting the need to study their long-term environmental impacts¹². It specifically highlights the possible impact of residues and additives on soil health

and microbial communities, and notes that even compostable materials can leave behind fragments or chemicals, emphasizing the need for further research into their behavior under real-world conditions.

Conversely, as plastics or BBMs age, their additives can leach out, making the materials unstable. Whilst in the case of conventional non-degradable plastics, this leads to further environmental pollution, BBMs can mitigate this impact through their biodegradability. Nevertheless, in both cases these additives can easily enter the food chain, particularly in oceans, where many organisms like fish and crustaceans filter water for nutrients. Many of which, such as phthalates, bisphenol A (BPA), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), are toxic to humans and ecosystems alike.

In Section V we present key recommendations to mitigate or eliminate remaining risks of chemicals in BBMs to unlock the full safety and sustainability potential of this promising group of materials.

Beyond chemical formulation, the fate of BBMs in the environment depends on how these materials break down or persist once disposed of, as well as what other EoL options such as recycling are possible. Section IV explores these end-of-life scenarios and how additives may interfere with intended biodegradation pathways.

High-Level Topic	Section II Finding	Language for Article 3
Safer alternatives to problematic plastics	BBMs that are free of chemicals of concern are credible, safe & sustainable alternatives to conventional plastics.	If a country proposes to include a chemical for phase out, or regulation under an Annexure linked to Article 3, the proposal must include information on an alternative which may be utilised if the regulation is adopted.
Hazard Minimisation & Chemical Safety	BBMs just as conventional plastics can contain chemicals of concern, including endocrine-disrupting phthalates and BPA. These substances are associated with long-term health impacts. These chemicals need to be phased-out.	Scope of Article 3 is sufficiently broad to capture conventional plastic and BBMs. Article 3 implements a mandatory phase out of chemicals such as BPA and phthalates.
Food Contact & Human Exposure Risks	Migration studies confirm leaching of harmful additives from conventional plastics and BBMs into food, posing dietary exposure risks. These chemicals need to be phased out.	Scope of Article 3 is sufficiently broad to capture conventional plastic and BBMs. Article 3 implements a mandatory phase out of chemicals such as BPA and phthalates.
Environmental Fate & Biodegradation Interference	Certain additives impair microbial activity, hindering biodegradation and causing longer environmental persistence of BBMs.	Scope of Article 3 is sufficiently broad to prevent plastic products which are not recyclable or compostable at scale, or may not be consistent with the principles of circular economy, from being exempt from Article 3.
Microplastic Formation & Bioaccumulation	Leaching of stabilizers and incomplete degradation can result in persistent microplastic fragments that bioaccumulate in ecosystems.	A key environmental risk articulated under Article 3 should be the risk to the environment, specifically microplastic persistence. Annexures should include a specific phase-out of products with intentionally-added microplastics.
Transparency & Traceability of Additives	Safety of BBMs depends on full disclosure of chemical composition, yet transparency is often lacking.	Article 3 should include a transparency requirement for the full disclosure of the chemical composition of BBMs.

Table 2: Section II Alignment with Article 3

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END OF LIFE AND ENVIRONMENTAL INTERACTION OF PLASTICS

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In 2019, 22 million tons of plastics were not properly disposed of and ended up in the environment worldwide¹³. Scientific studies have shown that plastics are transported by wind and rivers to remote regions, including Antarctica and Alpine glaciers¹⁴. Once released, plastics often accumulate in specific locations and begin to disintegrate over time under the action of temperature, pressure, and light. There are many well known examples, such as in oceans, rivers, lakes, and fields, where plastic products have shown to break down into macroplastics, microplastics, and eventually nanoplastics (<1 µm). Given the persistence and degree of penetration of these particles, another emerging issue is represented by atmospheric microplastic and nanoplastic pollution, which can spread through cloud formation and impact areas far removed from plastic production or disposal sites¹⁵. These

particles are invisible to the naked eye and the smaller they are the deeper they can penetrate biological barriers like plant walls but also animal organs and cells.

Designing safer materials is only part of the solution. What happens at the end of a product's life, whether it degrades, accumulates, pollutes or if it can be recovered and recycled, ultimately determines its environmental impact. This section examines the environmental fate of BBMs and the EoL strategies available for managing them. In line with the SSbD approach, BBMs must be evaluated not only by their intended applications but also by how they behave when mismanaged or released into the environment. First, there are certain applications where plastic materials are needed *in situ* and their environmental occurrence is not due to a mismatched

waste management strategy but they are released into the environment as part of their function. To avoid the release of toxic particles in water and soil, BBMs can offer a valuable alternative. BBMs that degrade harmlessly in the natural environment in a relatively short time, thanks to the enzymatic action of microorganisms, can be adopted in unique applications, e.g., as structures to support ecosystem and habitat restoration projects¹⁶. In agriculture, films made from BBMs release antifungal molecules while degrading¹⁷ and improve the storage and protection of seeds against fungal attack. For fertilizers, using BBMs allows for gradual release of nutrients over time, making them more effective¹⁸.

End of Life Management and Systems Compatibility

Beyond the intended environmental release, plastics also enter the environment through mismanagement or littering, particularly in regions where waste infrastructure is lacking or consumers are less aware or careless about the environmental impacts of mismanaged plastic waste. As littering remains common in some areas and while the long-term goal is to eliminate littering altogether, in the short term, replacing non-biodegradable plastics with BBMs can help reduce environmental harm where littering is still widespread. And whilst some sceptics argue that the use of BBMs could have the unintended effect that consumers see them as a *"license to litter"*

leading to a lower threshold of disposing these materials into the environment, these concerns seem to be unfounded. Recent studies have demonstrated that the type of material used is not a factor influencing the consumer's littering behavior¹⁹. While biodegradation is often seen as a defining feature of BBMs, it should not be viewed as their sole end-of-life pathway. In many cases, biodegradability serves as an environmental safety net, a form of EoL insurance against mismanaged waste, particularly in applications prone to littering. BBMs are increasingly designed to be compatible with conventional waste management infrastructure, including composting, mechanical recycling, and thermal recovery²⁰. Their integration into existing systems allows for more flexible and context-appropriate EoL strategies, depending on regional capabilities, product design, and environmental impact assessments.

Targeted collection and composting biodegradable packaging are sensible strategies where suitable facilities exist. Generally, biodegradable polymers have lower environmental impacts, as they degrade fully over time. The degradation process generally accelerates in environments with high microbial activity and at elevated temperatures for example in composting environments. Composting is a waste management strategy where organic waste is degraded into specific sites by the action of environmental

microbes to produce compost that finds application in the agricultural sector. Industrial composting facilities resemble home composting solutions, however on a larger scale that ensures higher temperatures and better aeration. These conditions allow industrial composting facilities to typically achieve better results than home composting. Biodegradable plastics can enter and degrade in composting facilities when they are collected with the organic waste fraction. Differently, if under anaerobic conditions, at specific industrial plants, more than half of biodegradable plastic can be converted into methane, a valuable, green energy carrier.

Alternatively, incineration can recover the inherent energy of the polymers through thermal recycling. The waste is burnt at very high temperatures, generating heat that can be used to make energy or supplied to households. The downside of incineration is, however, the generation and dispersion of Greenhouse Gases (GHGs). Overall, when LCAs indicate a neutral or negative carbon balance for the production of the BBM, incineration remains a viable option.

Recycling Pathways

Nevertheless, to keep material value in circulation for as long as possible, meaning to avoid environmental release, landfill end-of-life, or incineration, recycling is a crucial approach to minimize the loss of the energy and resources invested in

producing plastics. Several recycling methods are available for many types of BBMs including cellulose or PHA materials:

- Mechanical recycling, in which the material and additives are processed into new products. Often, virgin material must be blended in to maintain quality, since repeated processing can reduce the average molecular weight and weaken the material.
- Chemical recycling, where plastics are degraded into monomers using chemical agents and catalysts, potentially creating new chemicals or solvents. The use of high temperature and chemical agents, however, pose other concerns such as the energetic demand of the process and the generation of dangerous chemical wastes,
- Enzymatic degradation, which is particularly promising because it generates less harmful waste. Ideally, the resulting monomers can be purified and reused for polymerization through enzyme catalysis or even biosynthesis by microorganisms. Enzymatic degradation is so far kinetically too slow, presenting low yields, and hence not yet a competitive alternative.

4 STANDARDS AND CERTIFICATIONS: CLARITY, CREDIBILITY, AND SAFETY

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As discussed in the previous sections, the environmental performance of BBMs depends not only on polymer type (and chemical composition) but also on how the material behaves in real-world conditions. Particularly with the potential of BBMs as safer alternatives in high-volume, high environmental leakage applications makes thorough biodegradability assessment crucial. Correct testing, certifications, and labeling play a key role in strengthening safety measures. Additionally, an accurate communication of biodegradability standards and performance must occur to promote effective sustainable decisions and avoid any form of greenwashing²¹.

The Importance of Standards

Harmonized biodegradability standards are essential to ensure consistency, transparency, and credibility across geographies and product categories. To ensure the full environmental safety of

BBMs, biodegradation tests must be accompanied by chemical analyses (monitor the presence of harmful substances such as heavy metals, fluorine) and toxicity tests (which can be performed on marine, fresh water or soil micro-organisms, plants and animals). These standards then allow manufacturers, regulators, and certification bodies to test materials under reproducible and realistic conditions, helping verify whether a product truly degrades as claimed.

Internationally recognized standards, especially those developed by ISO (International Organization for Standardization), provide a scientifically robust and material-neutral basis for evaluation. When implemented in policy or procurement, they can create clear market signals while building trust among consumers, industry, and regulators.

Several key standard-setting bodies support biodegradability testing:

- **ISO** (International Organization for Standardization) – the preferred international framework, widely used across markets.
- **ASTM** (American Society for Testing and Materials) – common in North America.
- **CEN** (European Committee for Standardization) – EU-based but globally referenced.
- **National bodies** – such as the Australasian Bioplastics Association (ABA) or the Japan BioPlastics Association (JBPA), which apply region-specific adaptations.

While technical specifics vary, core test principles are aligned. For international recognition, ISO-compliant testing is recommended as the baseline.

Certification and Labeling

Compliance with recognized standards enables materials and products to be certified by independent third-party bodies. Certification provides a credible mechanism to verify biodegradability (and other sustainability claims) and builds trust across the value chain; from regulators and manufacturers to consumers.

To ensure integrity, certification involves three separate, independent parties: the **applicant** (e.g. manufacturer or brand), the **testing laboratory**, and the **certification agency**.

This separation ensures impartiality, prevents conflicts of interest, and

strengthens credibility. Certification confirms that a product not only meets technical biodegradability criteria but also does so under realistic and reproducible conditions.

Certification is available for a range of environments, including home composting, Industrial composting, soil, freshwater (e.g. from sewage systems), and marine environments.

The most established and widely recognized certification bodies include: **Europe:** DIN CERTCO (Deutsches Institut für Normung Certification Body), Seedling (by European Bioplastics) and TÜV AUSTRIA (Technischer Überwachungsverein Austria); **North America:** BPI (Biodegradable Products Institute); and **Asia / Australasia:** ABA and JBPA

It's important to note that certification is **application-specific**: a product can only be certified for an environment that is relevant to its intended use and likely end-of-life. Certification bodies also enforce strict rules on how claims can be marketed. For example, even if a plastic bag passes marine biodegradability tests, it cannot carry a marine biodegradability logo if it is not intended for marine use²². These safeguards help prevent greenwashing and ensure claims remain credible and scientifically grounded.

Matching Biodegradability Claims to Real-World Use

To ensure certification claims are both credible and meaningful, biodegradability must be evaluated in the context of how

and where a product is actually used and discarded. Different applications demand different biodegradation rates and environmental conditions, which means that a “biodegradable” label alone tells only part of the story. Importantly, the biodegradability of a material differs (rate and level) from one environment to another; hence, to address a realistic end-of-life behavior of the material, one must carefully select the appropriate standard of biodegradation depending on the polymer application in question²³.

A distinction can also be made between fast biodegradability (including composting), or slow biodegradability. In fact, for some applications, a fast or slow biodegradation can be the desired and best EoL option. Whilst in others, biodegradability is an added value or “littering insurance” that will ensure a full conversion into CO₂, biomass and water over time; as opposed to creating persistent microplastics that will remain in those environments for decades/centuries, affecting the fauna/flora and eventually entering the food chain^{24,25}. See Table 2 for examples.

It must be emphasized that not all materials that pass biodegradability tests are eligible for certification, and not all certified materials are appropriate for all applications. Certification must be both scientifically valid and contextually relevant²⁷. Certification agencies apply strict rules to how biodegradability claims can be marketed. Certification is only permitted when the claim aligns with the

product’s intended use and likely end-of-life. For example, even if a plastic bag passes marine biodegradability tests, it cannot be labeled as such if it’s not designed for marine use. Still, in the case of accidental littering, that bag may offer environmental benefits, such as avoiding the formation of persistent microplastics.

This shows that implementing credible, harmonised certification systems is critical to ensure BBMs deliver verified environmental benefits and to support the policy measures proposed in the following section. It is also crucial for manufacturers and brands to have clearer global guidelines which provide planning security and understanding how products can be marketed to have value-add for industry and the environment.

Use Case	Biodegradability Requirement	Examples
Compostable Applications	Fast biodegradation in managed / controlled environment	Tea bags, coffee pods, fruit/vegetable stickers
Products entering sewage system	Fast biodegradation in wastewater/sludge	Cosmetics, detergents
In-soil or aquatic applications	Slow biodegradation over extended time frames	Mulch films, fishing nets, aquaculture crates
Accidental leakage / littering	Biodegradation in uncontrolled environments as added value or “littering insurance”	Packaging, textiles, tire wear particles

Table 3: Use cases and biodegradability requirements for BBM product applications²⁶

5 EXPERT RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE GLOBAL PLASTICS TREATY

To ensure that bio-based and biodegradable materials (BBMs) support the treaty's goals of pollution prevention, human and environmental safety, and material circularity, we recommend the following:

1. Require Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approaches

Mandate the use of SSbD frameworks for all materials – plastics and BBMs – to ensure safety, sustainability, and circularity are embedded from the earliest design stages across environmental, health, social, and economic dimensions.

2. Mandate full chemical transparency and safety oversight

Require disclosure of all intentionally added substances and NIAS across the product life cycle, and support the development of a global “Red List” of hazardous chemicals which is applicable to both conventional plastics and their alternatives.

3. Support safer material innovation

Promote research, development, and adoption of inherently safer additives, formulations, and polymers to prevent regrettable substitutions and improve public and environmental health outcomes.

4. Implement harmonized standards and third-party certification

Require compliance with internationally recognized biodegradability and safety standards appropriate to the product's intended environment and application, verified through independent certification bodies.

5. Design for multiple end-of-life pathways

Encourage the development of alternatives and substitutes, including BBMs, that are compatible with regionally appropriate waste management infrastructure, such as industrial composting, mechanical recycling, or thermal recovery to ensure practical and flexible circularity.

6. Establish a science-based advisory mechanism

Create a standing scientific body to guide policy decisions, review emerging evidence on sustainability and performance of plastic alternatives, and recommend updates to treaty instruments (e.g., Red List, standards, certification criteria).

CASE IN POINT

Implementing the SSbD framework in practice

ViSS project (Project Grant No. 101081931-ViSS- HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-02-03. Co-founded by the European Commission. <https://viss-project.eu/>)²⁸ applies the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) methodology as a foundational and overarching framework to ensure that its bio-based plastics for food packaging are not only functional but also safe for human health and the environment, while delivering economic and social value. This holistic approach is integrated across the entire ViSS value chain, from feedstock sourcing to end-of-life scenarios.

By integrating these SSbD principles, the ViSS project directly contributes to the overarching goals of a plastic treaty by offering a concrete example of how plastic products can be designed to mitigate pollution, enhance circularity, eliminate hazardous substances, and ensure environmental and social benefits throughout their entire lifecycle.

ViSS has developed a six-step SSbD framework that defines clear principles, categories, aspects, and indicators for assessment. This framework covers safety, environmental, social, and economic

dimensions. Preliminary safety and sustainability assessments have already been conducted using this framework.

ViSS safety dimension covers two categories (health and environmental hazards) including indicators such as: acute toxicity, carcinogenicity, or hazardousness to the aquatic environment. ViSS includes safety by design including material by design to completely avoid toxic substances and minimize the use of hazardous ones in its PHBV (polyhydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate) extraction and formulation processes and process design considering worker safety and environmental releases during production. Finally, the safety dimension considers use and end of life. ViSS addresses consumer exposure and environmental harm at the product use and end-of-life stages. The biodegradability of ViSS PHBV in various environments (soil, freshwater, seawater, industrial and home compostability) is assessed to prevent the formation of microplastics and ensure an environmentally sound end-of-life.

ViSS sustainability dimension covers LCA, LCC and s-LCA. ViSS LCA (environmental dimension) includes the following categories: toxicity, climate change, pollution and resource use.

Several aspects have been decided to assess these categories, for instance: particulate matter formation, acidification, land and water use and the ecotoxicity in freshwater environments. ViSS S-LCA follows a Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment approach which covers workers, value chain actors, society, local community and consumers categories. To assess them a list of indicators has been followed (examples of these indications are: gender equality, fair price definition, technology transfer, the environmental management system, and transparency). Finally, ViSS LCC includes raw material and production costs.

The comprehensive evaluation of the SSbD dimensions is planned to be conducted in 2027 when solutions are fully developed. The ViSS approach demonstrates how the SSbD framework can be systematically applied to validate that BBMs deliver genuine environmental benefits whilst maintaining safety standards, economic viability and contributing to social sustainability. ViSS SSbD methodology includes the principles of Chair's Text Art. 5 on Plastic Product Design into the development of new plastic materials, aiming for a truly circular and sustainable bioeconomy.

In particular, the ViSS project's SSbD (Safe and Sustainable by Design) methodology directly implements the principles of Article 5 of the Chair's Text on Plastic Product Design by:

Designing for Circularity: ViSS develops PHBV, a bio-based and biodegradable polymer, from food industrial residues. This material is targeted for high-performance food packaging, with an emphasis on properties that support mechanical recyclability and environmentally sound end-of-life options like biodegradation, reducing plastic pollution.

Promoting Sustainable and Safe BBMs: ViSS is an innovation project specifically focused on creating a safer, bio-based alternative to conventional plastics, aligning with the call for sustainable alternatives and substitutes, such as BBMs.

Holistic Assessment: The SSbD framework ensures that ViSS considers the full lifecycle of PHBV, evaluating environmental (e.g., resource efficiency, minimizing microplastics), human health (e.g., safe additives), economic, and social aspects from the design stage. This proactive approach aims to avoid "regrettable substitutions" and contributes to a truly circular and sustainable bioeconomy.

Abbreviation	Meaning
ABA	Australasian Bioplastics Association
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BBMs	Biobased and Biodegradable Materials
BBP	Dibutyl Phthalate
BPA	Bisphenol A
BPI	Biodegradable Products Institute
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
DEHP	Di(2-ethylhexyl) Phthalate
DIN CERTCO	Deutsches Institut für Normung Certification Body
EoL	End of Life
GHG(s)	Greenhouse Gas(es)
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JBPA	Japan BioPlastics Association
JRC	Joint Research Centre (European Commission)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
NIAS	Non-Intentionally Added Substances
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PBAT	Polybutylene Adipate Terephthalate
PBDE(s)	Polybrominated Diphenyl Ethers
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PHA(s)	Polyhydroxyalkanoate(s)
PHBV	Polyhydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate
PLA	Polylactic Acid
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
TÜV AUSTRIA	Technischer Überwachungsverein Austria
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
ViSS	EU Project (Grant No. 101081931) on Value Chain for Safe and Sustainable PHBV

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